

64. Diyari

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Lit.: Austin, P. (1981). "A Grammar of Diyari, South Australia".

1. Segmental Properties

1.1 Phonotactic Patterns

- words must begin with a single C and end in V
- word-initial C may be a nasal, a stop or a semi-vowel except the apico-alveolar ones and /t^h/
- + exception: loan words
- e.g. *ɟapiti* "rabbit"

1.2 Phonological Processes

- morpheme final vowels are deleted before morphemes beginning in a vowel
- + final vowel of verb stem is omitted before derivational suffixes - *ɔɔɔ* (prolative) or - *ɔɔɔ* (transitivizer) (= "root vowel replacement")
- e.g. *ɔɔɔɔɔɔ* "to stand"
- ɔɔɔɔɔɔɔɔ* "to stand+TR"
- laterals and nasals may be prestopped if
- + they are apico-alveolar (/n/, /l/) or lamino-dental (/ɲ/, /ɳ/) and
- + they occur immediately after the first vowel of a word and are followed by a vowel and
- + the word-initial consonant is not a lateral or nasal respectively
- e.g. *ɔɔɔɔɔ* [ɲúɔɔɔɔɔ] ~ [ɲúɔɔɔ] "nose"

1.3 Default Syllable Template

- CV, CVC
- CVC not word-final
- all words contain at least 2 V
- + exception: *ɔɔ* "and"

2. Prosodic Properties

2.1 Stress

- primary stress
- + on first syllable
- secondary stress

- + on third syllable, if the word has at least four syllables
- + on first syllable of disyllabic suffix
- no morpho-syntactic function
- compounds are treated as separate pwords

2.2 Tone

none

3. Morpho-Syntax

3.1 Fusion

- all affixes appear to be phonologically bound, they fuse concatenatively

3.2 Non-Adjacent Allomorphy

none

3.3 Infixation, Circumfixation, Simulfixation

none

3.4 Reduplication

- first two syllables without coda of second syllable reduplicated: CV(C)CV
- root vowel replacement (see above) applies first

e.g. □□□□□□□□-□□□□ "to emerge"
 □□□□□□□□□□□□□□□□□□ "to emerge+PROL"

- reduplicated stems consist of two pwords, because

+ there are two primary stresses (on each first vowel)
 e.g. □□ú□□□□□□□□ú□□□□ "to emerge repeatedly"

+ pre-stopping of nasals applies twice
 e.g. □□□□□□□□□□□□□□□□ [□□□□□□□□□□□□□□□□□□] "little
 mother's mother"

3.5 Clitics and Particles

- 8 particles
 - + take no inflectional affixes
 - + can only be followed by post-inflectional affixes
 - + can occur in various positions: all can occur clause-initially, nearly all can occur at the second position, some can occur later in the clause, but normally to the left of the element they modify semantically, a few can occur clause-finally

- 8 post-inflectional affixes
 - + may be added to words of any class, except coordinators *ya* “and” and *kaja* “or”
 - + may be added after any other inflectional or derivational affix
 - + possible to add up to three of them

4. Other Questions

4.1 Unstressed Vowels

Nothing happens.

4.2 Word-Word Combinations

- only one compound verb: *waloo α pa-doo α ka* “to roll up, cover over” (*waloo α pa-* “to cover”, *doo α ka-* “to pierce”)
- phrasal compound nouns
 - + two juxtaposed nouns
 - e.g. *manoo α kira* “jawbone” (*manoo α* “mouth”, *kira* “boomerang”)
 - Nat5ata kanku* “younger brother” (*Nat5ata* “younger sibling”, *kanku* “boy”)
 - + noun + verb root (only two examples)
 - dooitJi doo α unoo α ka* “sunrise, east” (*dooitJi* “sun”, *doo α unoo α ka* “emerge”)
 - dooitJi widi* “sunset, west” (*dooitJi* “sun”, *widi* “enter”)

4.3 Bipartite Stems

none

4.4 Periphrastic Morphology

- 6 auxiliary verbs
 - + follow main verb optionally
 - + various tense and modal functions
 - + participial + AUX, non-finite future + AUX
- in the Dhirari dialect, the auxiliary *pudi-* obligatorily follows the main verb
- verb sequences
 - + up to three verbs in one verb phrase
 - + last stem takes inflection, previous stems take participial inflection *-noo α*
 - + only first root may have derivational affix, all others must be simple roots

4.5 Pre- and Postpositions

none

4.6 Pwords and Gwords

- pwords

- + must begin with C and end in V
- + primary stress on first V of pword
- + prestopping of nasals and laterals (see above)

- gwords

- + pauses
- + isolatability
- + permutation

- pwords and gwords coincide, except

- + conjunction *wa* ("and") which is a gword, but unstressed
- + reduplicated stems

4.7 Fast Speech Phenomena

- auxiliaries beginning with /wa/ change this to /u/ and contract with the preceding participial form

e.g. *n5ayin[∞]a wapaya* [n5√in[∞]√up√i√] "saw recently"

- the future auxiliary *Nana-* loses its initial consonant and contracts with the preceding stem, producing a long vowel

e.g. *n5ayil5a Nanayi* [n5√il5√:n√i] "will see"